

Report on the first Needs analysis

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Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Needs analysis purpose

Need analysis represents the part of the researchers' activities that follow the return phase, together with Focus group and Delphi study. Precisely, after each secondment to EU non-academic partner, upon returning to their home country, talents present the key issues and ideas from secondment phase and, together with researchers identify the situation and assess the needs of the business community in each widening country. For this, focus groups, needs analysis, Delphi study, systematic literature research and alike will be conducted.

Specific skills that should be gained during the secondments to EU countries are by far the most important soft element of Centers for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI centers), which will be established at each widening academic institution. Those skills represent EI centers core area, as a tool to create a bridge between academic institutions and business community. A combination of the right secondments and a return phase at the widening sending institution aims at (1) providing additional knowledge and skills (during the secondments) and (2) adapting this knowledge to the specific, local and national entrepreneurial ecosystem (e.g. while conducting systematic literature research, focus groups, Delphi study, needs analysis and alike).

Needs analysis is aimed at getting information about soft skills importance from the business community point of view. It is based on the questionnaire, which was produced as the result of the Delphi study. During period October – November, questionnaire was formulated and then used for collecting data. Data were collected in all four widening countries: Serbia, Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, North Macedonia.

Needs analysis should show which of the skills, previously identified and confirmed by experts, are considered as the most important by overall business community, regardless the industry type or size. The idea is to use the analysis results to decide which skills are the least developed and the most needed by the business community so have to be included into the training programme that will be composed under each Center for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI centers).

Research results – sample structure

Research refers to the sample of 100 companies, whereby 25 questionnaires were collected in each widening country. The following tables describe the sample.

Table 1. Number of companies by countries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Albania	25	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	25	25.0	25.0	50.0
	North Macedonia	25	25.0	25.0	75.0
	Serbia	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

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From the total number of companies in the sample, the majority refers to small companies (42), then large (30) and medium (28).

Table 2. Company size

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Large	30	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Medium	28	28.0	28.0	58.0
	Small	42	42.0	42.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Taking into account the company's activities, the largest participation in the sample have companies from the fields of Financial and insurance activities (16%), Information and Communications (12%) and Professional, scientific and technical activities (11%).

Table 3. Company's activity

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Area A: Agriculture, forestry and fishing	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
Area C: Manufacturing industry	9	9.0	9.0	13.0
Area D: Production and supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	2	2.0	2.0	15.0
Area E: Water supply, sewerage, waste management and environmental rehabilitation (remediation) activities	1	1.0	1.0	16.0
Area F: Construction	9	9.0	9.0	25.0
Area G: Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	6	6.0	6.0	31.0
Area H: Transportation and storage	3	3.0	3.0	34.0
Area I: Activities of providing accommodation, preparing and serving food, hotel and catering	1	1.0	1.0	35.0
Area J: Information and Communications	12	12.0	12.0	47.0
Area K: Financial and insurance activities	16	16.0	16.0	63.0
Area L: Real estate business	3	3.0	3.0	66.0
Area M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	11	11.0	11.0	77.0
Area N: Administrative and auxiliary service activities	1	1.0	1.0	78.0
Area O: Public administration and defense, compulsory social insurance	1	1.0	1.0	79.0
Area P: Education	9	9.0	9.0	88.0
Area Q: Health care and social work activities	4	4.0	4.0	92.0
Area S: Other service activities	7	7.0	7.0	99.0
Area U: Organization of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

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Considering the gender, the largest number of companies is managed by men, in 62% of cases.

Table 4. Gender structure of managers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	38	38.0	38.0	38.0
	Male	62	62.0	62.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The largest percentage of managers have Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities (32%), Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - social and humanities (22%) and Higher vocational education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities (16%). Only 5% of managers in the sample have Secondary education.

Table 5. Manager's education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - natural sciences	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Higher professional education - I cycle of studies - technical sciences	3	3.0	3.0	6.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - natural sciences	3	3.0	3.0	9.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - social and humanities	32	32.0	32.0	41.0
	Higher professional education - II cycle of studies - technical sciences	9	9.0	9.0	50.0
	Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - natural sciences	4	4.0	4.0	54.0
	Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - social and humanities	22	22.0	22.0	76.0
	Higher professional education - III cycle of studies - technical sciences	3	3.0	3.0	79.0
	Higher vocational education - I cycle of studies - social and humanities	16	16.0	16.0	95.0
	Secondary education	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

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Research results – statistical analysis

According to the research results and descriptive statistical analysis, all tested variables were rated very high (Table 6). The average ratings of all is higher than 4, except "How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals" received the lowest average rating. [c] Reference checks] (3.71). The highest average ratings achieved for the following variables: To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication skills] (4.73); To what extent are the following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills] (4.64) and How significant are soft skills for the following jobs? [b] Leadership and management] (4.60). Also, the standard deviation shows a high degree of agreement between the managers on the ratings of the tested variables. In this regard, the conclusion is that all variables are extremely important, as well as that the right variables were selected during the design of the survey questionnaire.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics of tested variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication_skills]	100	4.7300	.70861
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [b] Teamwork_skills]	100	4.4600	.80929
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [c] Adaptability]	100	4.4900	.88186
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional_intelligence]	100	4.2900	.96708
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [a] Human resources]	100	4.4500	.88048
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management]	100	4.6000	.79137
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [c] Customer service]	100	4.1600	.89578
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [d] CEO]	100	4.5000	.73168
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [a] Communication skills]	100	4.5400	.78393
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [b] Adaptability and flexibility]	100	4.5000	.79772
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [d] Team work and cooperation]	100	4.4500	.80873
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [e] Critical thinking]	100	4.3800	.85019
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [a] Building strong relationships]	100	4.2200	.83581
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [b] Contribution to teamwork]	100	4.3100	.83720
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]	100	4.4800	.87016
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [d] Opportunity for personal development]	100	4.3800	.87363

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4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [e] Resolving conflicts]	100	4.4100	.80522
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Encourage group projects]	100	4.1800	.88054
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b] Special courses and training programs]	100	4.1500	.83333
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs]	100	4.1700	.89955
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Special courses and training programs]	100	4.0500	.83333
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b]Mentoring one-on-one or in groups]	100	4.2500	.83333
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Active communication with employees]	100	4.4500	.84537
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [d] Being receptive to feedback]	100	4.4200	.80629
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [a] Openness to learning]	100	4.5300	.75819
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy]	100	4.1400	.91032
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [c] Communication skills]	100	4.5100	.82260
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [d] Adaptability]	100	4.4400	.72919
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [e] Self-awareness]	100	4.3300	.82945
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [a] Leadership skills]	100	4.4700	.86987
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [b] Communication skills]	100	4.5900	.82993
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [c] Emotional intelligence]	100	4.3300	.77921
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills]	100	4.6400	.74563

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8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [e] Teamwork]	100	4.2100	.85629
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [a] Communication skills]	100	4.5800	.75452
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [b] Team work]	100	4.3100	.80019
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [c] Adaptability and flexibility]	100	4.4000	.81650
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [d] Emotional intelligence]	100	4.2200	.78599
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [e] Problem solving skills]	100	4.4100	.84202
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing]	100	4.0400	.97359
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [b] Observation in team activities]	100	4.2600	.86012
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks]	100	3.7100	.95658
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [d] Detailed observation of communication and behavior]	100	4.4200	.87824

Taking into account the size of the company and the average ratings of the analyzed variables, it is concluded that all variables are very important regardless of the size of the company since average ratings in most cases are greater than 4 (Table 7). The following variables got the lowest ratings: How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing] (3.83 and only in the case of large companies) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (3.67 for large, 3.64 for medium and 3.79 for small companies). The biggest discrepancy in ratings between companies was found for variable: To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional intelligence], between large and medium-sized companies (4.5 and 4.0 respectively). In other cases, the difference in average ratings between companies of different sizes is less than 0.5.

Table 7. Average ratings by company size

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Company size	Large		Medium		Small	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication_skills]	4.7667	.77385	4.6786	.66964	4.7381	.70051
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [b] Teamwork_skills]	4.5000	.86103	4.5357	.74447	4.3810	.82499
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [c] Adaptability]	4.4667	.86037	4.3571	.95119	4.5952	.85709
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional_intelligence]	4.5000	.86103	4.0000	1.05409	4.3333	.95424
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [a] Human resources]	4.4667	1.00801	4.2857	.85449	4.5476	.80251
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management]	4.5333	.89955	4.5357	.74447	4.6905	.74860
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [c] Customer service]	4.0000	.94686	4.1429	.84828	4.2857	.89131
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [d] CEO]	4.4333	.81720	4.3571	.73102	4.6429	.65598
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [a] Communication skills]	4.5667	.81720	4.5357	.74447	4.5238	.80359
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [b] Adaptability and flexibility]	4.5333	.86037	4.4643	.69293	4.5000	.83374
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [d] Team work and cooperation]	4.5333	.81931	4.4643	.74447	4.3810	.85404
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [e] Critical thinking]	4.3000	.95231	4.2143	.83254	4.5476	.77152
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [a] Building strong relationships]	4.2000	.92476	4.1071	.83174	4.3095	.78050
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [b] Contribution to teamwork]	4.4333	.72793	4.3214	.81892	4.2143	.92488
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]	4.6333	.80872	4.5357	.79266	4.3333	.95424
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [d] Opportunity for personal development]	4.4667	.89955	4.1071	.87514	4.5000	.83374
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [e]	4.5000	.82001	4.2500	.84437	4.4524	.77152

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Resolving conflicts]						
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Encourage group projects]	4.1333	.93710	4.1071	.73733	4.2619	.93859
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b] Special courses and training programs]	4.2000	.88668	4.0714	.71640	4.1667	.88115
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs]	4.1000	.99481	4.0000	.90267	4.3333	.81650
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Special courses and training programs]	4.0333	.80872	4.0357	.69293	4.0714	.94721
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b]Mentoring one–on–one or in groups]	4.2000	.92476	4.1786	.81892	4.3333	.78606
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Active communication with employees]	4.4333	.89763	4.4286	.79015	4.4762	.86216
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [d] Being receptive to feedback]	4.4333	.85836	4.2857	.80999	4.5000	.77302
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [a] Openness to learning]	4.6000	.81368	4.3214	.72283	4.6190	.73093
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy]	4.2333	.89763	4.0000	.86066	4.1667	.96061

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7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [c] Communication skills]	4.5333	.86037	4.5714	.69007	4.4524	.88902
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [d] Adaptability]	4.4333	.81720	4.3929	.73733	4.4762	.67130
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [e] Self-awareness]	4.3333	.80230	4.2857	.80999	4.3571	.87851
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [a] Leadership skills]	4.6667	.66089	4.4286	.87891	4.3571	.98331
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [b] Communication skills]	4.6667	.80230	4.6071	.83174	4.5238	.86216
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [c] Emotional intelligence]	4.4667	.68145	4.1071	.78595	4.3810	.82499
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills]	4.8333	.74664	4.5000	.79349	4.5952	.70051
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [e] Teamwork]	4.2667	.86834	4.1429	.80343	4.2143	.89812
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [a] Communication skills]	4.7000	.79438	4.5714	.69007	4.5000	.77302
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [b] Team work]	4.3333	.80230	4.3571	.78004	4.2619	.82815
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [c] Adaptability and flexibility]	4.4333	.81720	4.4286	.79015	4.3571	.85029
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [d] Emotional intelligence]	4.3667	.71840	4.0714	.71640	4.2143	.87054

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9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [e] Problem solving skills]	4.5333	.86037	4.2857	.80999	4.4048	.85709
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing]	3.8333	1.01992	4.1429	.97046	4.1190	.94230
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [b] Observation in team activities]	4.3667	.88992	4.1429	.84828	4.2619	.85709
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks]	3.6667	.99424	3.6429	.95119	3.7857	.95088
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [d] Detailed observation of communication and behavior]	4.5000	.93772	4.2143	.87590	4.5000	.83374

As well previous results and the analysis of the average ratings of the variables achieved by country, shows enviable results, since in most cases in the analyzed countries the average ratings are above 4. The differences by the countries are analysed and presented in Table 8. The lowest rated variables in Albania are: To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional_intelligence] (3.88); How important are the following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [a] Building strong relationships] (3.96); According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the workplace soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Special courses and training programs] (3.96), To what extent are the following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [d] Emotional intelligence] (3.92), How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing] (3.84) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (3.60). Managers in Bosnia and Herzegovina the lowest mark gave to How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (3.88), while the lowest marks in North Macedonia are for variable According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the workplace soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Special courses and training programs] (3.80); How important are the following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy] (3.96) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (3.56). In Serbia, the lowest marks were given to variables How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [c] Customer service] (3.96) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (3.80).

Table 8. Average ratings by country

	Albania		Bosnia and Herzegovina		North Macedonia		Serbia	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication_skills]	4.5200	1.00499	4.9200	.27689	4.6400	.86023	4.8400	.37417
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [b] Teamwork_skills]	4.4000	1.00000	4.6800	.55678	4.2400	.92556	4.5200	.65320
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [c] Adaptability]	4.2800	1.20830	4.6800	.55678	4.4000	.91287	4.6000	.70711
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional_intelligence]	3.8800	1.23558	4.5600	.65064	4.4400	.76811	4.2800	1.02144
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [a] Human resources]	4.2800	1.10000	4.4400	.71181	4.5200	.96264	4.5600	.71181
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management]	4.3600	.90738	4.8000	.50000	4.6800	.85245	4.5600	.82057
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [c] Customer service]	4.2400	1.09087	4.0800	.70238	4.3600	.95219	3.9600	.78951
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [d] CEO]	4.3200	.90000	4.6800	.47610	4.5200	.71414	4.4800	.77028
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [a] Communication skills]	4.2800	1.06145	4.6000	.50000	4.4400	.91652	4.8400	.37417
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [b] Adaptability and flexibility]	4.2400	1.01160	4.6400	.48990	4.3600	.95219	4.7600	.52281
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern	4.2400	1.05198	4.6000	.50000	4.3600	.95219	4.6000	.57735

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business conditions? [d] Team work and cooperation]								
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [e] Critical thinking]	4.1600	1.02794	4.4400	.76811	4.3200	.85245	4.6000	.70711
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [a] Building strong relationships]	3.9600	.93452	4.4000	.76376	4.1600	.85049	4.3600	.75719
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [b] Contribution to teamwork]	4.2000	.91287	4.5600	.71181	4.0400	.97809	4.4400	.65064
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]	4.4800	1.00499	4.7200	.61373	4.2800	1.10000	4.4400	.65064
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [d] Opportunity for personal development]	4.2000	1.00000	4.6000	.57735	4.4400	1.00333	4.2800	.84261
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [e] Resolving conflicts]	4.4000	1.00000	4.6800	.47610	4.0800	.90921	4.4800	.65320
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Encourage group projects]	4.0400	.97809	4.3600	.63770	4.0000	1.04083	4.3200	.80208

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5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b) Special courses and training programs]	4.0000	.91287	4.4000	.70711	3.9600	1.01980	4.2400	.59722
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c) Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs]	4.0800	.99666	4.2800	.84261	4.2400	.96954	4.0800	.81240
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a) Special courses and training programs]	3.9600	.93452	4.4000	.70711	3.8000	.95743	4.0400	.61101
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b) Mentoring one-on-one or in groups]	4.1600	.98658	4.2400	.72342	4.2400	.87939	4.3600	.75719
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c) Active communication with employees]	4.3600	.99499	4.5200	.65320	4.3200	1.02956	4.6000	.64550

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6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [d] Being receptive to feedback]	4.2400	.96954	4.4800	.71414	4.3600	.86023	4.6000	.64550
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [a] Openness to learning]	4.2000	1.00000	4.6800	.47610	4.4800	.87178	4.7600	.43589
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy]	4.0400	1.05987	4.2800	.67823	3.9600	1.01980	4.2800	.84261
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [c] Communication skills]	4.4400	1.04403	4.6400	.56862	4.2800	.97980	4.6800	.55678
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [d] Adaptability]	4.3600	.99499	4.5200	.58595	4.3600	.75719	4.5200	.50990
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [e] Self-awareness]	4.2000	1.00000	4.2800	.54160	4.3200	.98826	4.5200	.71414
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [a] Leadership skills]	4.4000	.95743	4.5200	.65320	4.4000	.95743	4.5600	.91652

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8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [b] Communication skills]	4.4800	1.04563	4.6800	.55678	4.4400	.96090	4.7600	.66332
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [c] Emotional intelligence]	4.0800	.95394	4.4400	.58310	4.3200	.90000	4.4800	.58595
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills]	4.4800	1.04563	4.7600	.52281	4.6000	.76376	4.7200	.54160
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [e] Teamwork]	4.0800	.99666	4.3600	.63770	4.0800	1.03763	4.3200	.69041
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [a] Communication skills]	4.3600	.99499	4.8000	.40825	4.3600	.90738	4.8000	.40825
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [b] Team work]	4.2000	1.00000	4.4800	.50990	4.1200	.97125	4.4400	.58310
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [c] Adaptability]	4.3200	1.02956	4.5600	.50662	4.2800	1.02144	4.4400	.58310

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and flexibility]								
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [d] Emotional intelligence]	3.9200	.81240	4.4400	.65064	4.1200	.88129	4.4000	.70711
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [e] Problem solving skills]	4.2800	1.02144	4.6400	.56862	4.1600	1.06771	4.5600	.50662
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing]	3.8400	1.14310	4.3200	.69041	3.9600	1.13578	4.0400	.84063
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [b] Observation in team activities]	4.1200	.97125	4.5200	.65320	4.0400	.97809	4.3600	.75719
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks]	3.6000	1.11803	3.8800	.92736	3.5600	1.00333	3.8000	.76376
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [d] Detailed observation of communication and behavior]	4.2400	1.16476	4.5600	.58310	4.3600	.99499	4.5200	.65320

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Regardless of gender, all variables were rated highly, with scores higher than 4, except in the case of the How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing] (average rating 3.97 from the woman's point of view) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (average ratings according to both men and women are lower than 4, or 3.69 and 3.73 respectively). The analysis of the results based on the managers' gender is presented in Table 9.

For a smaller number of variables, the average ratings given by women are lower than average ratings given by men (only 23% variables were rated higher from the women point of view). Only the following 10 variables received higher average ratings from women compared to men: To what extent are the following soft skills important? [b] Teamwork_skills]; How important are the following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [d] Team work and cooperation]; How important are the following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [e] Critical thinking]; How important are the following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [b] Contribution to teamwork]; How important are the following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]; According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b] Special courses and training programs]; According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c]; Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs]; How important are the following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy]; To what extent are the following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [c] Emotional intelligence]; How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [b] Observation in team activities]. In addition, it is interesting that in the answers of women there is a high standard deviation, that is, quite a disagreement regarding the evaluation of the variables compared to men. Greater differences in the ratings given by men and women are present in the case of To what extent are the following soft skills important? [c] Adaptability] (4.29 rating from women and 4.61 rating from men) and How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management] (4.42 rating from women and 4.71 rating from men).

Table 9. Average ratings according to gender of the managers

	Female		Male	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication_skills]	4.6579	1.02077	4.7742	.42153
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [b] Teamwork_skills]	4.5000	1.03323	4.4355	.64327
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [c] Adaptability]	4.2895	1.18340	4.6129	.61016
1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [d] Emotional_intelligence]	4.2368	1.14925	4.3226	.84493

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2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [a] Human resources]	4.3421	1.12169	4.5161	.69523
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management]	4.4211	1.05604	4.7097	.55477
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [c] Customer service]	4.1053	1.13398	4.1935	.72063
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [d] CEO]	4.3421	.96636	4.5968	.52666
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [a] Communication skills]	4.4474	1.08297	4.5968	.52666
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [b] Adaptability and flexibility]	4.4474	1.05772	4.5323	.59279
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [d] Team work and cooperation]	4.5526	1.03185	4.3871	.63646
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [e] Critical thinking]	4.4211	1.03013	4.3548	.72647
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [a] Building strong relationships]	4.1842	.98242	4.2419	.73964
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [b] Contribution to teamwork]	4.3421	.99394	4.2903	.73300
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]	4.5000	1.08429	4.4677	.71787
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [d] Opportunity for personal development]	4.3684	1.05064	4.3871	.75433
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [e] Resolving conflicts]	4.3158	.96157	4.4677	.69466
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Encourage group projects]	4.1316	1.09473	4.2097	.72738
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b] Special courses and training programs]	4.1579	.97333	4.1452	.74320
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs]	4.2632	1.00497	4.1129	.83184
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Special courses and training programs]	4.0000	1.01342	4.0806	.70823
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [b]Mentoring one-on-one or in groups]	4.1579	1.02736	4.3065	.69161
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [c] Active communication with employees]	4.2632	1.10733	4.5645	.61726

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6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the work place soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [d] Being receptive to feedback]	4.3947	1.00107	4.4355	.66827
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [a] Openness to learning]	4.4211	1.05604	4.5968	.49455
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [b] Empathy]	4.1579	1.00071	4.1290	.85859
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [c] Communication skills]	4.3684	1.10089	4.5968	.58561
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [d] Adaptability]	4.3947	.94553	4.4677	.56446
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [e] Self-awareness]	4.2632	1.05739	4.3710	.65871
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [a] Leadership skills]	4.4737	.97916	4.4677	.80404
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [b] Communication skills]	4.4474	1.08297	4.6774	.62132
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [c] Emotional intelligence]	4.3684	.88290	4.3065	.71492
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills]	4.6053	.97369	4.6613	.57098
8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [e] Teamwork]	4.1842	1.06175	4.2258	.71102
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [a] Communication skills]	4.5000	1.05907	4.6290	.48701
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [b] Team work]	4.2895	1.06309	4.3226	.59435
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [c] Adaptability and flexibility]	4.3158	1.04248	4.4516	.64471
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [d] Emotional intelligence]	4.2105	.84335	4.2258	.75573
9. To what extent are following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [e] Problem solving skills]	4.3947	1.00107	4.4194	.73659
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing]	3.9737	1.15048	4.0806	.85504
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [b] Observation in team activities]	4.2895	1.01096	4.2419	.76148

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10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks]	3.7368	1.08264	3.6935	.87943
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [d] Detailed observation of communication and behavior]	4.3421	1.14553	4.4677	.67064

Conclusion

The secondments to non-academic partner ALDA, from France, highlighted the most important aspects and challenges concerning young people employment and skills development. The widening countries' subsequent situational analysis and needs assessment provided knowledge on specific contexts which R&I capacity should improve. Based on both types of activities, during the secondments and during the return phase, training programmes tailored to the specific business communities' needs and environment will be created by each sending institution in the widening country.

Specificities of each widening country, participating in the USE IPM project, will be taken into account when creating training programmes in at each academic institution, for each EI centre. However, certain conclusions, concerning soft skills importance, can be made for the whole Western Balkan region. They include the following:

Focus group:

In general, the respondents agree that soft skill are important for business sphere and should be developed during educational process as well as later, during the employment phase.

When examining the attitudes of respondents about the **necessary interpersonal and intrapersonal skills that are important for young people to successfully integrate into the world of work and run an entrepreneurial business**, it was found that effective **communication and social skills** are vital for **team dynamics, conflict resolution, and building customer relationships**. Furthermore, the respondents state that **personal integrity and persistence** are integral for professional **growth and achieving career** goals. Finally, they assert that **emotional intelligence** and **setting realistic objectives** contribute to long-term success in business.

When **examining the attitudes of respondents** regarding whether and which managerial skills and problem-solving skills are important for successfully starting and running a business, the respondents state that **planning and time management skills play critical roles** in achieving success, whether in business ventures or professional endeavors. However, the respondents believe that **time management skills should be more developed than they currently are**. Furthermore, the respondents emphasize that **problem-solving skills are essential for successful goal realization**, and different perspectives highlight various aspects of these skills. They also assert that **adaptability, effective communication, delegation, continuous learning, and focus contribute to effective problem-solving in different contexts**. Finally, they recognize the **significance of adapting to market shifts** in order to achieve business success. Entrepreneurs, in particular, understand the need for **flexibility and proactive adjustments** to stay competitive in a dynamic marketplace.

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The respondents state that **adaptability, creativity, and ongoing learning** contribute to overall success and they recognized that **innovative curricula** can also foster soft skills. While some respondents advocated for overlapping and reinforcing these skills across both educational and work phases, others drew a distinction between the soft skills needed during education and those required for effective job performance.

During the educational process, the following soft skills were emphasized:

- **Communication skills,**
- **Active listening,**
- **Creativity,**
- **Critical thinking,**
- **Resourcefulness,**
- **Passion,**
- **The ability to perceive a real-world view of business.**

In the context of professional development at work, the focus shifted to:

- **Resilience,**
- **Teamwork,**
- **Time management,**
- **Problem-solving,**
- **Effective networking,**
- **Financial literacy,**
- **Continual learning.**

Delphi study:

The experts agreed that it is not possible to ignore soft skills in modern business conditions presence of soft skills, as well as that soft skills are more important than hard skills for some jobs, such as: **Human resources, Leadership and management, Customer service, Marketing, CEO**. Also, they all undoubtedly claim that it is difficult to assess an individual's soft skills.

As individuals' desirable skills demanded by modern business conditions, experts listed the following ones:

- **Communication skills**
- **Adaptability and flexibility**
- **Emotional intelligence**
- **Teamwork and collaboration**
- **Critical thinking**

As tools for building and strengthening soft skills, experts recommended combination of **Special courses and training programs, Encouraging group projects and workshops, Combination of typical classroom learning/training programs, Practicing assertive communication.**

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For starting and successfully running business, experts found especially important: Leadership skills, Communication skills, Emotional intelligence, Problem-solving skills, Teamwork. In comparison with the skills identified as preferable during the evaluation by the HRM service in the selection process, including Communication skills, Teamwork, Adaptability and flexibility, Emotional Intelligence and Problem solving skills, it can be said that some of the skills are equally important for both, running entrepreneurial business and managing the company. Those skills are: **Communication skills, Emotional intelligence, Problem-solving skills, Teamwork.**

Needs analysis:

The following table points the options with the highest rank under each question. Due to the frequency of its appearance, it can be concluded that **Communication skills** have the highest rating as the most important soft skill generally, as the most important soft skill of entrepreneurs in modern business conditions, as well as the most important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process. **Detail observation of communication and behaviour** is also important for assessing/recognizing the soft skills of individuals. Except communication, **Problem solving skills** are highly ranked as important for starting and successfully running own business. Soft skills are considered the most important for **Leadership and management** (as job titles) and their development is mostly targeting **employees' motivation**. The business representatives claim that the most important for the successful development of soft skills of individuals is **Openness to learning**. In addition, the most of the interviewees claim that the formal education system can contribute to the soft skills building and strengthening through **Encouraging group projects**, while in the workplace soft skills can be build and strengthen through **Active communication with employee**.

Table X. Soft skills with highest average scores

1. To what extent are the following soft skills important? [a] Communication skills]	100	4.7300	.70861
2. How significant are soft skills for following jobs? [b] Leadership and management]	100	4.6000	.79137
3. How important are following soft skills of individuals in modern business conditions? [a] Communication skills]	100	4.5400	.78393
4. How important are following reasons for developing soft skills in the workplace? [c] Motivating staff]	100	4.4800	.87016
5. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should in the formal education system soft skills building and strengthening activities be approached? [a] Encourage group projects]	100	4.1800	.88054
6. According to your opinion and experience, in which of the following ways should the activities of building and strengthening soft skills in the workplace be approached? [c] Active communication with employees]	100	4.4500	.84537
7. How important are following prerequisites (personality traits) for the successful development of soft skills of individuals? [a] Openness to learning]	100	4.5300	.75819

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8. To what extent are following soft skills important for starting and successfully running your own business? [d] Problem solving skills	100	4.6400	.74563
9. To what extent are the following soft skills important for positive evaluation by the human resource management service in the selection process? [a] Communication skills	100	4.5800	.75452
10. How important is each of following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [d] Detailed observation of communication and behaviour	100	4.4200	.87824

Based on the results of the all four activities (Systematic literature review, Focus groups, Delphi study and Needs analysis) it can be concluded that at least two or three training programmes should be focused on developing **communication skills, team work skills, problem solving skills, critical thinking, time management, emotional intelligence.**

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